

Stability Indicating Method Development and Validation of Tedizolid Phosphate in Bulk and Tablet Dosage Form By RP-HPLC Method

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ABSTRACT

Objective: The present study aimed to develop and validate a simple, accurate, precise, and stability-indicating reversed-phase high-performance liquid chromatographic (RP-HPLC) method for the quantitative estimation of Tedizolid Phosphate in bulk and tablet dosage forms, along with its degradation behaviour under stress conditions. **Methods:** Chromatographic separation was performed on a C18 column (250 × 4.6 mm, 5 μm) using a mobile phase of water, acetonitrile, and methanol (65:20:15 v/v/v) containing 0.1% triethylamine (TEA) at a flow rate of 0.7 ml/min. Detection was carried out at 299 nm with a UV detector. The method was validated as per ICH Q2(R1) guidelines for linearity, precision, accuracy, robustness, ruggedness, LOD, and LOQ. Forced degradation studies were conducted under acidic, alkaline, oxidative, reductive, and photolytic conditions. **Results:** Tedizolid Phosphate showed a sharp, symmetric peak at 2.483 minutes. The method was linear over the range of 20–100 μg/ml with a correlation coefficient (r²) of 0.9998. Precision (%RSD <1.5%) and accuracy (recoveries 98.42–101.15%) confirmed the reliability of the method. LOD and LOQ were found to be 3.3179 μg/ml and 10.0544 μg/ml, respectively. Forced degradation results indicated major degradation under reducing conditions, while the drug was comparatively stable under other stress conditions. Degradation peaks were well separated from the main peak, confirming the method's stability-indicating nature. **Conclusion:** The developed RP-HPLC method is simple, robust, and reliable, making it suitable for routine quality control and stability assessment of Tedizolid Phosphate in bulk and tablet formulations.

Keywords: Tedizolid phosphate, RP-HPLC, Forced degradation, Validation, ICH guidelines, Pharmaceutical dosage form.

INTRODUCTION

Tedizolid Phosphate (Fig.1) is [(5R)-3-[3-fluoro-4-[6-(2-methyltetrazol-5-yl) pyridin-3-yl] phenyl]-2-oxo-1,3-oxazolidin-5-yl] methyl dihydrogen phosphate]. Its molecular formula is C₁₇H₁₆FN₆O₆P and molecular weight is 450.32 g/mol.

Fig.1. Chemical structure of Tedizolid phosphate

Multidrug-resistant Gram-positive bacteria pose a major global health concern and are responsible for a substantial proportion of hospital-acquired infections, leading to significant morbidity and mortality. Among these, Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) and Vancomycin-resistant enterococci (VRE) are particularly challenging due to their resistance to commonly available antibiotics. Although drugs such as linezolid and daptomycin have been effectively utilized over the past decade, the emergence of resistance to these agents, though still limited, has been increasingly reported in clinical practice. Consequently, there is an urgent need for novel antibacterial agents capable of combating MRSA and VRE infections.

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Oxazolidinones represent a synthetic class of antibiotics introduced in the past three decades, with linezolid being the first approved compound of this group. Linezolid exhibits broad-spectrum activity against multidrug-resistant Gram-positive organisms and is widely prescribed for complicated skin and soft tissue infections (cSSSI), community-acquired pneumonia, hospital-acquired pneumonia, and VRE-associated infections.

Tedizolid phosphate, a next-generation oxazolidinone and the first of its kind approved by the U.S. FDA, was developed to overcome certain limitations associated with linezolid. Despite structural similarities, tedizolid demonstrates greater potency, fewer adverse effects during short-term administration, and improved pharmacokinetic properties. These advantages position tedizolid as a valuable therapeutic option for the management of serious infections caused by resistant Gram-positive bacteria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Instrumentation

The analysis was performed on a Shimadzu HPLC system (LC-20AD) equipped with a UV-Visible detector and operated through LabSolutions software. Chromatographic separation was carried out using a Shimadzu C18 column (250 × 4.5 mm, 5 μm). A Shimadzu AUX-220 electronic balance was used for weighing, and ultrasonication was carried out using a laboratory sonicator. Stability and degradation studies were conducted employing a hot air oven (InfraDIGI, up to 250 °C) and a UV light chamber.

Reagents and Chemicals

All reagents and solvents were of HPLC grade and sourced from Qualigens India Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai. Pure Tedizolid Phosphate was generously supplied by a pharmaceutical company, Mumbai, while STARIZO® tablets (each containing 200 mg of Tedizolid Phosphate) were purchased from a local pharmacy. The solvents and chemicals utilized included HPLC grade water, HPLC grade acetonitrile, 0.1% triethylamine (TEA), 0.1 N sulfuric acid, 0.3% hydrogen peroxide, 10% sodium bisulfate, and 0.1 N potassium hydroxide

METHOD OPTIMIZATION

The chromatographic method was optimized by systematically varying different parameters, including mobile phase composition, detection wavelength, diluent and flow rate, to achieve sharp, symmetric peaks with suitable retention time and resolution.

Mobile phase Optimization

Several combinations of water, methanol, and acetonitrile, with and without acidic modifiers, were evaluated. Mobile phases without modifiers exhibited tailing and peak broadening. Incorporating 0.1% TEA improved peak symmetry and reproducibility. The optimized mobile phase—water, acetonitrile, and methanol (65:20:15 v/v/v) containing 0.1% TEA—produced sharp, symmetric peaks with appropriate retention time and resolution

Selection of Diluent

HPLC grade water was chosen as the diluent to ensure complete solubility, compatibility, and consistent chromatographic behaviour.

Selection of Wavelength

The UV absorption spectrum of Tedizolid Phosphate (200–400 nm) displayed a maximum at 299 nm, which was selected as the detection wavelength for optimal sensitivity and minimal baseline noise

Optimization of Flow Rate

Flow rates from 0.5–1.0 ml/min were examined. Higher flow rates resulted in decreased resolution, whereas lower rates prolonged analysis time. A 0.7 ml/min flow rate provided an ideal balance and was adopted for the final method.

Final Optimized Condition

The finalized chromatographic parameters included a Shimadzu C18 column (250 × 4.5 mm), a mobile phase of water, acetonitrile, and methanol (65:20:15 v/v/v) containing 0.1% TEA, a flow rate of 0.8 ml/min, UV detection at 299 nm, and an injection volume of 20 μL. These conditions yielded sharp, symmetric peaks and met all ICH system suitability criteria.

Analytical Method Development

Preparation of Mobile Phase

The mobile phase was prepared by combining water, acetonitrile, and methanol (65:20:15 v/v/v) with 0.1% TEA, filtered through a 0.45 µm membrane, and degassed by sonication prior to use.

Preparation of standard stock solution

An accurately weighed 200 mg of Tedizolid Phosphate was transferred to a 100 ml volumetric flask, dissolved in HPLC grade water, and diluted to volume to yield a 2000 µg/ml stock solution.

Preparation of working solution

From the stock, 5 ml was transferred to a 50 ml volumetric flask and diluted to obtain a 200 µg/ml working solution.

Preparation of sample solution

Twenty tablets (each containing 200 mg Tedizolid Phosphate) were weighed and powdered. Tablet powder equivalent to **200 mg** was transferred to a **100 ml volumetric flask** containing diluent, sonicated for **15 minutes**, and diluted to volume with water to form a **sample stock solution**. The solution was filtered, and appropriate dilutions were prepared to achieve concentrations of **200 µg/ml** and **40 µg/ml**. The absorbance of the sample solution was recorded at **299 nm**, and drug content per tablet was calculated by applying the dilution factor.

METHOD VALIDATION

System Suitability

System suitability was confirmed by injecting the standard solution under optimized conditions. Tedizolid Phosphate showed a sharp, symmetric peak at 2.483 min with theoretical plates >2000 and a tailing factor <2.0, complying with ICH acceptance limits.

Linearity

Linearity was determined over a range of **20–100 µg/ml** by preparing dilutions from the standard stock solution (200 µg/ml). Calibration curves were plotted between **peak area vs. concentration**, showing good linear correlation.

C. Precision

Precision was assessed by analysing **six replicates** of a 40 µg/ml solution. The %RSD values of the peak areas were within acceptable limits (<2%), confirming method repeatability.

D. Accuracy

Accuracy was established using the **standard addition method** at **50%, 100%, and 150%** concentration levels. Tablet powder equivalent to 200 mg was spiked with known amounts of standard drug, analysed in triplicate, and recovery percentages were within **98–102%**

E. Robustness

Robustness was evaluated by making slight variations in chromatographic parameters:

- **Mobile phase ratio:** ±1 ml (66:21:13 and 67:19:14 v/v/v)
- **Detection wavelength:** ±1 nm (298 nm and 300 nm)
- **Flow rate:** ±0.1 ml/min (0.6 and 0.8 ml/min)

The %RSD values were <2%, with no significant variation in peak shape or retention, confirming robustness.

F. Ruggedness

Ruggedness was verified by analysing the 40 µg/ml sample solution using **two analysts** and **two instruments** under identical conditions. Results demonstrated reproducibility.

G. LOD & LOQ

LOD and LOQ were calculated in accordance with ICH guidelines using the standard deviation (σ) of the y-intercept and the slope (s) of the calibration curve:

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 \times \sigma / s$$

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \times \sigma / s$$

Where:

σ = the standard deviation of the response

s = the slope of the calibration curve

4.2.2.13 Forced degradation studies

Acidic Degradation ^[13]

From the 200 µg/ml working solution, 2 ml was mixed with 2 ml of 0.1 N H₂SO₄ and kept for 24 hours. The solution was neutralized with 0.1 N KOH, diluted, and injected into the HPLC.

Alkaline Degradation ^[13]

2 ml of the 200 µg/ml solution was treated with 2 ml of 0.1 N KOH, kept for 24 hours, neutralized with 0.1 N H₂SO₄, diluted, and analysed.

Oxidative Degradation ^[13]

2 ml of working solution was mixed with 2 ml of 0.3% H₂O₂, kept for 24 hours, diluted with diluent, and injected to monitor oxidative degradation.

Reductive Degradation ^[14]

2 ml of working solution was combined with 2 ml of 10% sodium bisulfate, kept for 24 hours, diluted to mark, and analysed.

Photolytic Degradation ^[14]

Raw Tedizolid Phosphate was exposed to sunlight for 4 hours, followed by preparation of a 200 µg/ml solution, which was analysed to assess photolytic degradation.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Method development and optimization

The HPLC method was systematically optimized to achieve effective separation and accurate quantification of Tedizolid Phosphate in tablet formulations. Different solvent ratios of **methanol, acetonitrile, and water** were tested (Table 1). The optimized mobile phase provided well-resolved, symmetric peaks with consistent retention time and satisfactory system suitability parameters.

Table 1: The different ratios of mobile phase tried and remark on obtained peaks

S. No	Mobile phase composition	Flow rate	Interference
1	Water: Acetonitrile: Methanol (60:15:25) with 0.1% formic acid	1 ml/min	Peak elute late and RT is 12.601
2	Water: Acetonitrile: Methanol (55:25:20)	1 ml/min	Peak elutes early and RT is 1.725
3	Water: Acetonitrile: Methanol (40:30:30) with 0.1%OPA	1 ml/min	Peak to be splitted and RT is 6.467
4	Water: Acetonitrile: Methanol (65:20:15) with 0.1%TEA	1 ml/min	Proper peak shape, peaks Baseline noise reduced, tailing factor less than 2 but RT is 1.842.
5	Water: Acetonitrile: Methanol (65:20:15) with 0.1%TEA	0.7 ml/min	Proper peak shape, peaks Baseline noise reduced, tailing factor less than 2 but RT is 2.483.

The optimized chromatogram for Tedizolid phosphate is presented in **Figure 2** (blank) and **Figure 3** (optimized chromatogram)

FIGURE 2: Chromatogram for Blank

FIGURE 3: Optimized chromatogram for Standard

Method Validation

The developed HPLC method for Tedizolid Phosphate was validated following ICH Q2(R1) guidelines

System suitability

System suitability was assessed by evaluating chromatographic parameters such as **tailing factor** and **theoretical plates**. The results of these evaluations are summarized in **Table 2**.

Table 2: System suitability parameters of Tedizolid phosphate

Parameters	Results
Number of theoretical plates or efficacy	2704
Tailing factor	1.782
Retention time	2.483
Peak area	941338

Linearity

The developed method demonstrated excellent linearity, with a regression equation of $y = mx + c$ and a correlation coefficient ($R^2 = 0.9998$), indicating its suitability for precise quantitative analysis. The corresponding data are summarized in Table 3. Calibration curves, constructed over the concentration range of 20–100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, are depicted in Figure 4. Key analytical parameters, including the slope, intercept, correlation coefficient, LOD, and LOQ, are presented in Table 4.

Table 3: Calibration curve data for Tedizolid phosphate

Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Peak Area
20	206171
40	389381
60	580799
80	771391
100	969194

Figure 4: Calibration curve for Tedizolid phosphate

Table 4: Optical parameters and linearity data of Tedizolid phosphate

Parameters	Tedizolid phosphate
Beer's law range (µg/ml)	20-100
Regression equation (y=mx + c)	Y = 9618x-5224
Slope	9618
Intercept	5244
Correlation coefficient (r ²)	0.9998
Standard error	3947.92
Limit of detection (µg/ml)	3.3179
Limit of quantification (µg/ml)	10.0544

Precision

System precision was evaluated by performing **six replicate injections** of a **12 µg/ml** Plecanatide

solution. The resulting **%RSD of 0.6542%** was well within acceptable limits, confirming the method's precision (**Table 5, Figure 5**).

Table-5: Precision of Tedizolid phosphate Formulation

Sample no	Label claim (mg)	Amount found (mg)	% Purity	% Average	SD	% RSD
1	200	199.29	99.64	100.11	0.6550	0.6542
2		201.15	100.57			
3		201.25	100.62			
4		198.29	99.14			
5		201.6	100.8			
6		199.84	99.92			

* Mean of 6 Observations

Figure 5: Precision chromatogram for Tedizolid phosphate

Accuracy

Accuracy was assessed using the **standard addition method** at three different concentration levels, with

each level analyzed in **triplicate**. The **mean percentage recovery** of Tedizolid Phosphate was found to be within acceptable limits, confirming the accuracy of the developed method (**Table 6**)

Table-6: Accuracy (recovery) data for Tedizolid phosphate

Sample	% Concentration	Sample amount (µg/ml)	Amount spiked (µg/ml)	Estimated amount (µg/ml)	Recovered amount (µg/ml)	Average % Recovery	SD	%RSD
TED	50	40	20	59.92	19.92	99.6	0.3	0.3012
	100	40	40	80.69	40.69	101.72	0.4154	0.4083
	150	40	60	99.84	59.84	99.73	1.2895	1.2895

* Mean of 3 Observations

Robustness

Robustness was assessed by making deliberate variations in flow rate (± 0.1 ml/min), wavelength (± 1 nm), and mobile phase composition (± 1 ml). The

%RSD values remained within acceptable limits, demonstrating that the method is robust. The robustness results are presented in Table 7.

Table-7: Robustness data for Tedizolid phosphate

PARAMETER	AMOUNT FOUND (mg/tab)	% PURITY	SD	% RSD
FLOW RATE				
0.6 ml/min	200.98	100.49	0.6801	0.6801
0.7 ml/min	200.80	100.4	0.7217	0.7214
0.8 ml/min	200.42	100.04	0.9832	0.9832
MOBILE PHASE COMPOSITION				
Acetonitrile: Methanol: Water (21:13:66 % v/v/v) with 0.1%TEA	201.83	100.91	0.4760	0.4747

Acetonitrile: Methanol: Water (20:15:65 % v/v/v) with 0.1%TEA	200.52	100.26	0.5106	0.5092
Acetonitrile: Methanol: Water (19:14:67 % v/v/v) with 0.1%TEA	199.82	99.91	1.1320	1.1330
WAVELENGTH				
298 nm	200.88	100.43	1.1836	1.1785
299 nm	199.86	99.92	0.7724	0.7730
300 nm	200.60	100.30	1.0908	1.0908

*Mean of 3 Observations

Ruggedness

Ruggedness was evaluated under varied conditions, with %RSD values within acceptable

limits, confirming good reproducibility. The results are presented in Table 8.

Table-8: Ruggedness data for Tedizolid phosphate

Sample	Concentration (µg/ml)	Type of Ruggedness*	Average % recovery*	SD	% RSD
TED	40	Analyst 1	99.34	0.7421	0.7389
		Analyst 2	99.95	1.0747	1.0752
		Instrument 1	100.65	0.7311	0.7263
		Instrument 2	100.04	0.2306	0.2305

*Mean of 3 Observations

FORCED DEGRADATION STUDIES

Forced degradation studies were performed to assess the stability of Tedizolid Phosphate under various stress conditions. The drug exhibited significant degradation under **acidic and reductive conditions**, while remaining stable under **alkaline,**

oxidative, photolytic, UV, and thermal stress. These results confirm that the developed **RP-HPLC method** is capable of distinguishing the drug from its degradation products and is therefore **stability-indicating**. Detailed findings are summarized in **Table 9**, with corresponding chromatograms shown in **Figures 6–12**.

Table 9: Degradation data for Tedizolid phosphate

Stress condition	Time interval	Degradation
Acidic degradation	24 hrs	Not degraded
Alkali degradation	24 hrs	Not degraded
Oxidation degradation	24 hrs	Not degraded
Reduction degradation	24 hrs	Degraded
Photolytic degradation	04 hrs	Not degraded

<Chromatogram>

mV

<Peak Table>

Detector A 299nm

Peak#	Ret. Time	Area	Height	Conc.	Unit	Mark	Name
1	2.725	378508	46522	0.000	mg/L	M	TEDIZOLID PHOSPHATE
Total		378508	46522				

Figure 6: Acid degradation chromatogram of Tedizolid phosphate

<Chromatogram>

mV

<Peak Table>

Detector A 299nm

Peak#	Ret. Time	Area	Height	Conc.	Unit	Mark	Name
1	2.733	232868	23708	0.000	mg/L	M	TEDIZOLID PHOSPHATE
Total		232868	23708				

Figure 7: Alkali degradation chromatogram of Tedizolid phosphate

<Chromatogram>

mV

<Peak Table>

Detector A 299nm

Peak#	Ret. Time	Area	Height	Conc.	Unit	Mark	Name
1	2.517	416973	20723	0.000	mg/L	M	TEDIZOLID PHOSPHATE
Total		416973	20723				

Figure 8: Oxidative degradation chromatogram of Tedizolid phosphate

<Chromatogram>

mV

<Peak Table>

Detector A 299nm

Peak#	Ret. Time	Area	Height	Conc.	Unit	Mark	Name
1	3.767	652467	36485	0.000	mg/L	M	TEDIZOLID PHOSPHATE
Total		652467	36485				

Figure 9: Reduction degradation chromatogram of Tedizolid phosphate

Figure 10: Photolytic degradation chromatogram of Tedizolid phosphate

CONCLUSION

A simple, precise, and robust RP-HPLC method was successfully developed and validated for the quantitative estimation of Tedizolid Phosphate in both bulk drug and tablet formulations. The method was optimized using a mobile phase of water, acetonitrile, and methanol (65:20:15 v/v/v) containing 0.1% TEA, with UV detection at 299 nm and a flow rate of 0.7 ml/min, yielding sharp, symmetric peaks with a retention time of 2.483 min. The method exhibited excellent linearity over the concentration range of 20–100 µg/ml ($R^2 = 0.9998$). Validation parameters, including system suitability, precision, accuracy, robustness, and ruggedness, were all within ICH acceptance criteria, confirming the method's reliability. Forced degradation studies revealed that Tedizolid Phosphate was prone to degradation under reductive conditions, while remaining stable under acidic, alkaline, oxidative and photolytic stress, demonstrating the method's stability-indicating capability. In conclusion, the developed RP-HPLC method is accurate, reproducible, and stability-indicating, making it highly suitable for routine quality control and stability studies of Tedizolid Phosphate in pharmaceutical formulations.

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AUTHORS CONTRIBUTIONS

All the authors have contributed equally.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

Declared none.

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